

Comparison of nutrient quality between new and stored grains in japonica rice

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The current emphasis of breeding programs in the major rice-producing countries has shifted from increasing yield to improving quality to increase market value. It is well known that the eating quality of rice undergoes a remarkable change during storage. The eating quality of stored rice deteriorates with changes in various chemical characteristics. It was reported that the appearance, aroma, taste, cohesiveness, and hardness of stored rice deteriorate during storage and this deterioration could be predicted by evaluating changes in some chemical characteristics. Introducing indica-type or early maturing traits to japonica cultivars would lower the linoleic acid content and prevent storage deterioration.

Up to now, only a few reports have focused on differences in deterioration of the eating quality of stored rice among ordinary cultivars. No reports exist on changes in nutrient quality for recently developed superior cultivars with good eating quality. This study was conducted to determine the differences in nutrient quality characteristics among cultivars stored for about 8 mo at room temperature. Seven cultivars of japonica rice were used in this experiment: Koshihikari, Hanaecheizen and Etsunan 162 (recently developed in Japan, with good to excellent palatability), and Xiushui 11 and Xiushui 27 (with ordinary eating quality in China). These cultivars were grown in 1996 at the experimental field of the Rice Breeding Department of FAES. All cultivars were transplanted in mid-May

and harvested in late September. The moisture content of fresh brown rice and stored rice for the sensory test was about 13.5%. For storage, rice was hulled and kept in iron boxes at room temperature for about 8 mo.

All analyses were conducted in November 1996 for new rice and from May to June 1997 for stored rice. Amylose and protein content were measured by near-infrared reflectance spectroscopy (NIRS). Free fatty acid content was measured following the method of Matsue (1990).

The mean amylose content of new and stored rice was 19.7% and 19.4%, respectively (Table 1). The mean protein content of new and stored rice was 6.4% and 6.2%. There seemed to be no difference in amylose and protein content during postharvest storage. This consistency in both protein and amylose content between stored and new rice showed that

deterioration of the eating quality could not be attributed to protein and amylose content.

Table 1 shows free fatty acid content of new and stored rice. Free fatty acid content of milled rice (mg %) varied from 14.6 to 25.0 for a new crop and from 19.8 to 39.7 for stored rice. Free fatty acid content of all cultivars increased and variation among cultivars widened during storage. Free fatty acid content in stored rice seed of Xiushui 27 and Xiushui 11, which had ordinary eating quality, was high, but that of Koshihikari, Hanaecheizen, and Etsunan 162, which had better eating quality, was low. The coefficient of correlation between overall eating quality and free fatty acid content of stored rice was -0.890^{**} (Table 2). Therefore, palatability of stored rice could be partly evaluated by measuring its free fatty acid content.

Table 1. Amylose, protein, and free fatty acid content of new and stored rice.^a

Cultivar	Amylose (%)		Protein (%)		Free fatty acid (mg %)	
	New rice	Stored rice	New rice	Stored rice	New rice	Stored rice
Koshihikari	18.0	17.5	5.6	5.5	17.6	19.8
Akihikari	17.2	17.3	6.6	6.5	21.7	26.0
Nihonbare	20.7	19.8	6.2	6.3	25.0	30.9
Xiushui 27	23.9	23.6	6.8	6.6	14.6	39.7
Xiushui 11	19.4	20.4	7.3	7.0	20.8	34.7
Hanaecheizen	19.5	18.9	6.4	6.4	21.9	24.9
Etsunan 162	19.2	18.6	5.9	5.6	23.5	26.2
Mean	19.7	19.4	6.4	6.2	20.7	28.9

^aValues of amylose and protein were % weight basis for milled rice.

Table 2. Coefficient of correlation among eating quality factors and free fatty acid content of stored rice.

Trait	Ara	T	S	H	OEQ
Free fatty acid (FFA)	-0.379	-0.196	0.201	0.183	-0.890**
Aroma (Ara)		0.716*	0.297	-0.215	0.182
Taste (T)			0.694*	-0.463	0.948**
Stickiness (S)				-0.735*	0.906**
Hardness (H)					-0.137

* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$. OEQ = overall eating quality.